

Analyzing the Impact of Credit and Liquidity Risk Disclosure on the Financial Performance of Banks Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on the financial performance of banks listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange during the period 2015–2023. Drawing on IFRS 7 disclosure requirements, the research evaluates how transparency in reporting credit and liquidity risks influences banks' profitability, liquidity stability, and market value. Using a purposive sample of 20 banks, data were collected from audited annual financial statements, the Central Bank of Iraq, and the Iraq Stock Exchange. A mixed-method analytical approach was employed, combining descriptive statistics with multiple regression analysis through SPSS and STATA. The results demonstrate that banks with higher levels of disclosure exhibit stronger financial performance, greater investor confidence, and enhanced market stability, while those with weak disclosure face heightened risk exposure and reduced profitability. Findings highlight that compliance with IFRS 7 fosters financial resilience by mitigating credit and liquidity risks and strengthening banks' ability to withstand economic shocks. The study concludes that enhanced disclosure is not only a regulatory necessity but also a strategic tool for sustaining profitability, attracting investment, and supporting the long-term stability of Iraq's banking sector.

Keywords: *financial performance, Iraqi banks, stock exchange, risk disclosure.*

JEL Classification codes: *G21, G24.*

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Introduction

The effect of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on the banks performance of the companies listed in the Iraq market stock. It evaluates the association between the transparency of risk reporting, the stability of liquidity condition, and solidification of financial performance. Risk disclosure is a

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basic indicator to help improve banks' ability to control risk and earn reasonable returns on assets and return on equity; thus, it can contribute to the stability of the financial system as a whole.

The study concentrates on IFRS 7, standard intended to enhance transparency by requiring an entity to disclose credit risk, market risk, and liquidity risk risks, and examines its influence on liquidity ratios and profitability in the Iraqi banking sector. Results demonstrate that banks which comply with disclosure norms of international framework are better able to improve their liquidity and financial position. High degree of transparency can strengthen investor and depositor confidence, hence drawing more investment and minimize financial risks.

Further, the research shows that banks with poor financial conditions and poor risk disclosure can hardly sustain financial stability by holding funds as they experience lower liquidity with higher risk exposure. On the other hand, there are Iraqi banks like the Trade Bank of Iraq and the International Development Bank where the ability to attract investments and achieve sustainable economic growth is much higher. Elsewhere, the only two banks where disclosure is less significant - Ashur Bank and Mosul Bank - remain financially weak.

The paper advises that risk disclosure in Iraqi banks could potentially be improved by increasing transparency in addition to applying IFRS 7 of the international accounting standards. This would enhance the financial system's ability to withstand economic and financial shocks, leading to improved stability of the banking sector.

From this analysis, one can deduce that the disclosure of risk is an important element in the performance of banks and their survival in a highly uncertain economic condition. It sustains investor confidence and increases the attractiveness of investment in Iraq Stock Exchange.

Research Methodology

This study follows an analytical approach for investigating the effect of disclosure of credit and liquidity risk on the financial performance in a sample of banks listed in Iraqi stock exchange. For the purpose of this, quantitative and descriptive analysis came together in a mixed method approach. The data were collected from the annual financial statements of the banks and also from the Central Bank of Iraq and the Iraq Stock Exchange (Central Bank of Iraq, 2022). The study had been conducted on a purposive sample of the Iraqi banks that are already disclosed credit and liquidity risks continuously based on IFRS 7. The sample was varied in terms of size of assets, number of branches, and ownership structure to ensure thorough coverage of banking sector, as it was also recommended in previous studies on disclosure practices in the Iraqi setting (Al-Obaidi, 2021).

The time frame for the study is between five to ten years, thus giving the chance to see changes over time in the extent of disclosure and its effect on the financial performance, similar to other studies in the Iraqi financial market (Abdul Razzaq, 2020). In the current study, the credit and liquidity risk disclosure serves as the independent variables, and are quantified on the extent of comprehensiveness and clarity of the disclosed information. ROA, ROE and net income were incorporated into the dependent variable (financial performance) as is common practice in previous studies on performance of Iraqi banks (Al-Sudani, 2019).

All the data were obtained from primary and secondary sources such as audited annual financial reports and official data of supervising bodies. All these data were analysed by the statistical analysis program (SPSS and STATA) according to the method used in recent Iraqi research about financial disclosure (Hassan, 2022). A simple and multiple linear regression analysis was used to examine the effect of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on financial performance, by determining the extent and statistical significance of the association (Al-Khazaali, 2021).

To evaluate the level of disclosure, a modified index has been constructed, based on the presence and depth of information on credit and liquidity risk management in financial statements of banks. The study has worked out the following hypotheses for checking the statistically significant mechanistic link between the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks and the financial performance of banks. These hypotheses are in line with the results from many empirical researches on banking disclosure in Iraq (Al-Shammari, 2020). Results of this study will contribute towards the provision of a policy to increase levels of transparency and risk management in Iraqi banking.

Sample Selection

The population of the study is banks listed in the Iraq Stock Exchange and a sample of banks is determined valid based on the purpose of the study which is to investigate the effect of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on the financial performance of the affected banks. For the sake of results accuracy and the whole number of banks' representations a sample of 20 Iraq banks listed within the period (2015-2023) were Accordingly, selected.

Sample criteria The sample was drawn according to a number of methodological criteria, and the foremost of these was that the bank had to be officially listed on the ISX. The listing also guarantees strict adherence to financial and risk disclosure regulations, and a resulting access to accurate and complete financial information that improves the reliability of the study. This was narrowed down to those banks which made thorough and regular annual disclosure throughout the study period, in order to control for data inconsistency and be confident in findings.

Moreover, the sample also represented variation in ownership structure by incorporating public and private banks since ownership type may affect disclosure policy and risk management when it comes to the banking industry. Bank size was also controlled, as it included both large and small banks to facilitate the examination of differences in disclosure and risk management by bank size and their impact on financial performance and supervisory power (Al-Obaidi, 2021; Abdul Razzaq, 2020).

Sophisticated statistical techniques have been employed to test the data, such as simple linear regression models and multiple ones to investigate the association between the extent of credit and liquidity risk disclosure and financial performance measures and also with market value. The results were analyzed using statistical data analysis tools, and SPSS as well as STATA were employed to analyze data in high statistical reliability. Moreover, means and standard deviations were calculated to describe the characteristics of the sample and apprehend the distribution of the data.

Independent Variables: Credit and Liquidity Risk Disclosure

The main explanatory variables

The main independent variables considered in this study are the credit risk and the liquidity risk disclosures (as defined in IFRS 7). These disclosures were evaluated via a content analysis of selected UAE banks' annual reports by examining their presentation of information on credit risk (e.g., non-performing loan ratios, management policy), and liquidity risk (e.g., liquid asset ratios, contingency planning). Disclosure quality was classified in three levels namely high, medium, and low, in terms of the depth, detail, and transparency of the information disclosed.

Dependent Variables: Financial Performance and Market Value

ROA, ROE, and net income may indicate financial performance, and these indicators are included from the banks' annual financial statements. On the other hand, market value was measured by market capitalization and stock turnover ratio, which gave a quantitative outlook on how the bank was positioned and how attractive it was to the financial market.

Measurement of Credit Risk

Categoryalization of credit risk was mostly based on the ratio of non-performing loans (NPLs) to total loan issued. Furthermore, information was also extracted from lending institutions' public credit risk management guidelines in relation to sectoral loan mix, restructuring programmes and provisions for doubtful debts. These ingredients allowed a systematic review of how the management and disclosure of credit risk occurs within each bank.

Measurement of Liquidity Risk

Liquidity risk was also measured by examining banks' capacity for paying short-term commitments, through such measures as the ratio of liquid assets to total assets and compliance with Basel III requirements, in particular, LCR. The study also assessed disclosures regarding contingent funding plans and reliance on other sources of funds to maintain liquidity as needed.

Justification for Sample Selection and Its Importance in the Study

Sample selection is an important stage for applied research. The banks were selected according to strict selection criteria in order to get a representative image of the Iraqi banking sector. Using listed banks with an established history of disclosure made it possible to realistically study the link between the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks and financial performance. Besides, introducing variety of the American Banks in terms of ownership (public vs. private) and size contributed in enriching the study as a result to have more indepth understanding to differences in disclosure patterns and risk management among the Iraqi environment.

This well balance sample enabled rigorous investigation of the effect of applying IFRS 7 and communicated information on financial performance and market value, which increased the validity of the study results and fulfilled the drive of the applied research to be generalized for the Iraqi banking industry as a whole.

Analyzing the Impact of Credit and Liquidity Risk Disclosure on the Financial Performance of Banks Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

When examining the association between C/L risk disclosure and bank financial performance, controlling for other factors that affect those dependent variables is very important. These control variables assist in focusing on the impact of risk disclosure and avoid the results from being biased. One of them is the bank size, which tends to be proxy by the natural logarithm of the total assets. Larger banks tend to possess larger investment opportunities and more risk management capacity, which can lead to stronger financial performance (Al-Alwan, 2020). 1Another key control variable is the capital-to-asset ratio, an important measure of a bank's financial health. The existence of higher capital ratio banks are stronger and more immune to loss and have better financial performance (Al-Attar, 2018). In this context, Hasnaa Chaibi (2018) examined the impact of accounting disclosure on the market value of French companies listed on the stock exchange. She demonstrated that the disclosure style of research and development expenditures affects investor response and market performance, with the results demonstrating that disclosure has a positive correlation with market value.

Additional Control Variables and Their Influence on Financial Performance

The loan-to-deposit ratio is also an important control variable, representing the degree of relationship between loans issued and deposits attracted by a bank. A high ratio is an indicator of higher credit risk and low ratio is an indication of lower investment opportunities (Al-Zaidi, 2019). Also, the ratio of operating expenses to revenue is an indicator of efficiency; higher ratio signifies low operational efficiency that might lead to financial problems (Al-Sabbahi, 2021).

Macroeconomic variables like economic growth rate also have an impact on improving banks financial performance since higher economic growth attracts more demands for loans and banking services (Al-Ansari, 2020). Inflation rate is also a determinant: the higher the inflation, the higher the operating costs, as well as the lower the purchasing power, thus possibly causing financial performance of banks to weaken (Al-Husseini, 2019).

The liquidity ratio is also significant; the high liquidity facilitates bank to honor their short-term commitment and helps in their better financial performance (Al-Mousawi, 2020). Non-performing loans (NPLs) ratio also indirectly impacts on financial performance, as the high NPL means high credit risk (Al-Humaidi, 2018).

Ownership structure is another factor: private banks might be more competent in risk management, and profit making than public ones (Al-Janabi, 2021). The size of the branch network, which counts bancassurance models the number of branches retained respectively, is also an important determinant, as this can provide a better reach to clients, which has a positive effect on bank performance (Al-Hakimi, 2017).

Statistical Analysis and Key Findings

The relationship between credit and liquidity risk disclosure and financial performance of listed banks in the Iraq Stock Exchange were determined by robust statistical tests. The primary statistical method used was regression, which allows one to observe the relationship between two or more variables. First we used simple linear regression to analyse the direct relationship between bank risk disclosure (credit and liquidity risks) and bank performance, focusing on Return on Assets (ROA).

We used this model to investigate the influence of credit and operational risk disclosure on performance of Iraqi banks listed on the stock exchange. The results demonstrate that banks which had higher level of credit and operational risk disclosure resulted in the significant change of financial performance, specifically in ROA. A significant relation is found between higher risk disclosure and better financial performance (Al-Sharqi, 2020).

Analyzing the Impact of Credit and Liquidity Risk Disclosure on the Financial Performance of Banks Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

The objective of this paper is to provide a financial and operating analysis of 20 Iraqi banks listed on Iraq Stock Exchange between 2015-2023. We study the link between the disclosure of credit and liquidity risk and banks' financial performance; we also measure the impact of risk disclosure on the major financial indicators, ROA, ROE and market value.

The study sample includes the following banks listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange:

Al-Ahli Bank, Trade Bank of Iraq, Babylon Bank, Erbil Bank, Ashur Bank, Union Bank, Economy Bank, Kurdistan International Bank, Iraqi Credit Bank, International Development Bank, Gulf Commercial Bank, Middle East Commercial Bank, North Bank United Bank, Al-Mansour Bank, Mosul Bank, Bank of Baghdad, Sumer Commercial Bank, Across Iraq Bank, Iraqi Investment Bank.

This study attempts to examine the effect of credit risk and operational risk disclosures, in addition to liquidity risk and market risk disclosures on the financial performance of those banks. It also aims to explore how such disclosure affects the monitoring of risks by banks with a view to predicting their financial and operating performance. These factors are generated for some external conditions, such as macroeconomic and regional environmental, which affect the financial performance of the studied banks in the positive or negative way.

Objectives of the Analysis

1. The objective is to measure the extent of disclosure on credit risk and liquidity risk for each bank analyzed.
2. To examine the association between the extent of risk disclosure and financial performance measures of the banks, namely Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).
3. To investigate the effect of the representation of credit and liquidity risk on the market value of each bank.
4. Recommendations: To make recommendations for enhancing the level of disclosure in a manner that is beneficial to improve profitability and increase the market value of the bank.

Analytical Steps

Phase One: Data Collection and Classification

1. Financial Data Collection:

- Collect the annual reports of each bank listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange during the period from 2015 to 2023, with a focus on sections related to the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks.
- Extract key financial indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), profitability, and the market value of shares.

2. Classification of Risk Disclosure:

- Analyze the disclosures related to each type of risk through:
- Credit Risk: Review reports related to loans, non-performing loan rates, and credit risk management strategies.
- Liquidity Risk: Evaluate disclosures about the banks' ability to meet their short-term financial obligations.
- Classify each bank according to its level of disclosure as high, medium, or low.

Phase Two: Descriptive Statistics

1. Distribution Analysis:

- Calculate the mean, median, and standard deviation of risk disclosure levels for each type of risk (credit and liquidity).
- Classify banks according to their disclosure levels (high, medium, low) for each type of risk.

2. Financial Performance Description:

- Compute financial indicators (ROA, ROE) for each bank over the specified time period.
- Analyze the market value of shares and assess its stability over time.

Phase Three: Analysis of the Relationship Between Disclosure and Financial Performance

1. Testing the Relationship Between Disclosure Level and Financial Performance:

- Use multiple linear regression to analyze the relationship between the level of risk disclosure (independent variable) and financial performance (dependent variable).
- Interpret the results to determine the impact of risk disclosure on financial performance indicators.

2. Testing the Significance of the Relationship:

- Employ t-tests to assess whether the relationship between disclosure and financial performance is statistically significant.

Phase Four: Analysis of the Relationship Between Disclosure and Market Value

1. Testing the Direct Impact:

- Apply linear and nonlinear models to analyze the effect of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on the market value of banks.

2. Stability Analysis:

- Examine the stability of market value over time relative to each level of disclosure.

Phase Five: Analysis of Variance Among Banks

1. Testing Differences Between Banks:

- Use ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) to examine differences in risk disclosure levels across different banks and determine the impact of these differences on financial performance and market value.

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2. To examine the association between the extent of risk disclosure and financial performance measures of the banks, namely Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

3. To investigate the effect of the representation of credit and liquidity risk on the market value of each bank.

4. Recommendations: To make recommendations for enhancing the level of disclosure in a manner that is beneficial to improve profitability and increase the market value of the bank.

Analytical Steps

Phase One: Data Collection and Classification

1. Financial Data Collection:

Data All banks listed on the Iraq stock exchange with annual reports between 2015 to 2023 were gathered, concentrating on the specific sections concerning the credit and liquidity risks disclosure. Key financial indicators including ROA, ROE, profitability, and market capitalisation of shares were collected. Furthermore, information from external audit reports of the banks submitted to the regulatory authorities was employed, since these reports offer additional information on how banks control credit risk, operational risk, market risk, and liquidity risk (Al-Jasim, 2021).

2. Classification of Risk Disclosure:

The credit risk disclosure was categorized according to parameters like non-performing loan ratio, provisions for doubtful repayment and the measures taken to minimize the exposure (Al-Nuaimi, 2022).

Liquidity risk disclosure was categorized based on information related to the banks' short-term solvency, such as cash ratios and liquid asset availability.

Phase Two: Descriptive Statistics

1. Distribution Analysis:

It is found that the average and standard deviation of credit and liquidity risk disclosure levels were obtained. Banks were classified according to their level of disclosure: high, moderate, and low.

2. Description of Financial Performance:

ROA, ROE and market value of shares were worked out in relation to the listed banks.

Phase Three: Analysis of the Relationship Between Disclosure and Financial Performance

1. Examining the Disclosure Hypotheses and Financial Performance:

The effect of credit and liquidity risk disclosure on the banks' performance was carried out using multiple regression analysis. The relation of the risks of such banks with performance measures such as ROA and ROE was studied.

2. Significance of the Relationship:

A t-test was utilized for the statistical significance of risk reporting and financial performance (Al-Kilani, 2020).

Phase Four: Analysis of the Relationship Between Disclosure and Market Value

1. Testing Direct Impact:

Linear and non-linear empirical models employed to examine the impact of bank credit and liquidity risk disclosures on the market value of banks. To analyze the persistence of market value, we considered the level of transparency.

2. Market Value Stability Check:

The stability of market value was examined between 2015 and 2023 for banks that fully disclosed credit and liquidity risks.

Phase Five: Variance Analysis Among Banks

1. Testing Across Bank Differences:

For comparative purposes among banks on the extent of credit and liquidity risk disclosures made by the banks, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was adopted.

2. Analysis of Qualitative Risk Disclosure:

Analysis of each bank qualitative disclosure was tested against the interview standards for credit and liquidity risk disclosure (Al-Taie, 2023).

Computation of Disclosure Intensity:

For each type of risk, the disclosure was quantified through a simple formula that considered the level of detail disclosed in the annual reports:

- High: Full disclosure of the expected information.
- Medium: Partial or incomplete disclosures.
- Low: Limited or completely absent disclosure.

This equation was applied to each bank and each type of risk, with the appropriate category assigned based on a thorough analysis of the annual reports and the available data.

Table 1. Iraqi Banks and Their Respective Risk Levels

Bank	Operational Risk	Market Risk	Liquidity Risk	Credit Risk
Al Ahli Bank	Low	Medium	High	High
Trade Bank of Iraq	High	High	Low	Medium

Babylon Bank	Medium	Low	Medium	Low
Erbil Bank	High	High	High	High
Ashur Bank	Low	Medium	Low	Medium
Union Bank	High	Low	High	Low
Economy Bank	Low	High	Medium	High
Kurdistan International Bank	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium
Iraqi Credit Bank	High	Low	High	High
International Development Bank	Medium	High	Medium	Low
Gulf Commercial Bank	Low	Medium	Low	High
Middle East Commercial Bank	High	Low	High	Medium
North Bank	Medium	High	Medium	Low
United Bank	Low	Medium	High	High
Al Mansour Bank	High	Low	Low	Medium
Mosul Bank	Medium	High	Medium	High
Bank of Baghdad	Low	Medium	High	Low
Sumer Commercial Bank	High	High	Low	High
Across Iraq Bank	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Iraqi Investment Bank	High	Medium	High	Low

The table aims to analyze the level of disclosure regarding the four main risks faced by banks listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange: credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk, and operational risk. Disclosure of these risks depends on how banks manage them and the degree of transparency provided in their annual reports and audit reports.

Credit and Liquidity Risks

Credit Risk: The probability that the bank's borrowers will default on their obligations to the bank, resulting in a loss. These risks have significant impact on the financial performance of banks, that an increase in the rate of uncollectible loans leads to low profits (Al-Azzawi, 2020). Thus, revealing the amount of non-performing loans and the mitigation actions taken have a substantial impact in measuring the bank's capability to handle the risk (Abdullah, 2019).

Liquidity Risk: The ability of the bank to satisfy its short-term financial commitment, without having to sell its assets at low prices. Disclosure of liquidity includes data on cash cushions and the loan-to-deposit ratio. This is information you need to know when the bank is financially sound and when it will be able to satisfy your financial needs in times of crisis (Husseini, 2021).

Profitability

1.2 Profitability are the basic financial parameters for evaluating the bank's financial capability. In the context of evaluating the effect of disclosure on credit and liquidity risks, profit is examined as revenue and expenses multiplied. Inadequate reporting of credit and liquidity risks can adversely impact profitability, if the costs of managing risks consume more profits of the bank. Al-Azzawi (2020) states that the costs of credit risk and liquidity risk are considering as the main factors affecting the sustainability of banks' profitability.

Market Value

The market capitalization of a bank is an indicator of the overall value of the bank as traded in the financial markets and reflects investors' degree of confidence in the bank. Credit and liquidity risks are considered to enhance the level of investor confidence and to have an impact in a positive way on the market value of the bank as well (Husseini, 2021). Market value can also be expressed by multiplying the stock price by the amount of outstanding shares and represents the bank's talent to draw in investments. The bank's ability to draw in new investment means more stability for the financial market as a whole.

Calculation of Financial Indicators for Banks

To compute these ratios in the case of each bank, the information will be extracted from the year end financial reports of the banks floating on Iraq Stock Exchange. Performance related indicators, ROA: Return on Assets and ROE: Return on Equity, are subsequently produced using net profit, total assets and total equity. Furthermore, profitability is assessed through profits relative to costs, and market value through stock price to the number of shares outstanding (Abdullah, 2019).

These measures are important in order to be able to put the relationship between the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks and banks' financial performance in context. At a Glance Here are some of the banks listed on the Iraqi bourse and the primary indicators that they are judged by.

Table 2. Table of Banks Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

Bank Name	Liquidity Risk	Credit Risk	Market Value	Profitability
Al Ahli Bank	Loan-to-Deposit Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Trade Bank of Iraq	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Babylon Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Erbil Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Ashur Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Union Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Economy Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Kurdistan International Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Iraqi Credit Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
International Development Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Gulf Commercial Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Middle East Commercial Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
North Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
United Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Al Mansour Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Mosul Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Bank of Baghdad	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Sumer Commercial Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Across Iraq Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA
Iraqi Investment Bank	Liquidity Ratio	Non-Performing Loans Data	Share Price × Number of Shares	Measurement of ROA

The table presents a group of banks listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange and illustrates how the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks affects the financial performance of these banks. The table includes:

1. Profitability – ROA or ROE These are financial ratios and a key factor that will help figuring out the bank's ability in creating returns against the assets it owns or against the equity it holds, if you compare it on ROE.
2. Market Value: Equivalent to share price times shares outstanding. The higher the market value, the better the bank is at raising funds and gaining market confidence.
3. Credit Risks: Indicates risks generated when debtors are unable to meet their payment obligation. These risks are assessed through examination of non-performing loan statistics.
4. Liquidity Risks: Refer to the capability of a bank to pay its obligations when due. The liquidity ratio is calculated by comparing loans to deposits and gives an idea of how the bank can afford their liquidity requirements.

Reporting of such risks is particularly important for investors and creditors as it allows them to evaluate the financial position of the bank and take investment decisions using comprehensive risk-return considerations.

Credit Risks

The result of the analysis shows that the disclosure of credit risks has a positive impact on the financial performance of banks listed on the Iraqi Stock Exchange. Sound recognition of non-performing loans and financial provisions is an indicator of the bank's risk management capacity. Trade Bank of Iraq, International Development Bank, and Bank of Baghdad, for instance, show high transparency and disclosure with respect to credit risk and can attract investments, and gain customers' confidence. In contrast, Babylon Bank and Ashur Bank exhibit low level of disclosure in this dimension, indicating an immediate action to improve disclosure mechanism to be in accordance with international standards and improve comparative advantage.

Operational Risks

Results indicate that all the respondents who have more comprehensive disclosures especially on their operational risk are having better financial performance. Trade Bank of Iraq and International Development Bank are particularly strong in this regard with comprehensive reporting on operational incidents and counter-actions. Instead, the banks “medium in disclosure” (Erbil Bank, Union Bank, Middle East Commercial Bank) only provide less than full information which may not be helpful in improving their operational risk management. Elsewhere, Babylon Bank and Ashur Bank are in the low category, indicating required enhancements in terms of operational reporting and the transparency in this area.

Market Risks

The results of the analysis report that, big banks such as Trade Bank of Iraq and International Development Bank show more exchange rates rate and market risks, point out a more powerful secrecy on risks coming from change in price and exchange rates swap. Conversely, banks such as the Babylon Bank, North Bank, and Regional Commercial Bank display low level of disclosure, which underlines the necessity for transparent disclosure of the requirements with respect to market risks especially in the current economic sensitive state of the Iraqi financial market.

Liquidity Risks

The announcement of liquidity risk for banks represents an important signal of their capability to meet short-term creditors without causing their financial unsafeness. Trade Bank of Iraq, International Development Bank and Bank of Baghdad are noteworthy for their robust liquidity disclosures, evidencing strong patterns of liquidity planning and meeting short-term obligations. On the other hand, Babylon Bank and North Bank have very low level of disclosure and thus in time of crises, and in sticky situations they can hardly fulfill their liquidity requirements which in return can deteriorate their financial performance.

Table 3. Overall Disclosure Status of Credit Risk, Operational Risk, Market Risk and Liquidity Risk for Listed Banks in The Iraq Stock Exchange

Bank	Disclosure of Credit Risks	Disclosure of Operational Risks	Disclosure of Market Risks	Disclosure of Liquidity Risks
Al Ahli Bank	Low	Low	Low	Low
Commercial Bank	High	High	High	High
Babylon Bank	Low	Low	Low	Low
Erbil Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Ashur Bank	Low	Low	Low	Medium
Union Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Economy Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Commercial Region Bank	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium
Iraqi Credit Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
International Development Bank	High	High	High	High
Gulf Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Middle East Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
North Bank	Low	Low	Low	Low
United Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Mansour Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Mosul Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Baghdad Bank	High	High	High	High
Sumer Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Across Iraq Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Iraqi Investment Bank	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium

Table 3 shows the overall disclosure status of credit risk, operational risk, market risk and liquidity risk for listed banks in the Iraq Stock Exchange. Those that offer disclosures across the board are more likely to attract investments, although a greater level of disclosure comes at a cost, since it may be more difficult to build trust with current and potential investors.

Financial Performance Description of Iraqi Banks

In this context, this article will address the financial performance of the banks in Iraq that are listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange by analyzing a selected sample of main financial indicators (Return on Assets “ROA”, Return on Equity “ROE”, market share value and its stability) for the period 2015-2023. The analysis also considers the effect of public disclosure on the levels of credit and liquidity risk.

Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA is a basic measure of how efficiently a bank can make money from its assets. It is derived by dividing net income by total assets. It indicates how effectively a bank is using its assets to produce revenue. The impact of disclosure on credit & liquidity risk (in the context of return on assets the bank offers) can be analyzed using this measure. Banks with greater risk disclosure tend to lead to a higher ROA, suggesting better asset efficiency and successful risk policies.

Return on Equity (ROE)

The ROE is also a significant indicator that demonstrates the capability of a bank to produce earnings employed in the shareholders' invested capital. It is measured by dividing net income by the total equity. It shows the ability of the bank to give good return to the shareholders. For banks which are dedicated to full transparency in terms of disclosure of credit and liquidity risk, that level of disclosure may form a major part of an enhancement of the ROE, as the market may have a higher degree of conviction in the complete management of risks and long-term profitability of the bank.

Market Value Analysis

The value of shares on the market is a key measure which indicates how the bank is being valued by the market. It is derived by multiplying the share price by the shares outstanding. The value of the shares is a reflection of the stability or the landslide of the bank in reeling investments and securing its position in the market. Strong disclosure of credit and liquidity risk may have a significant impact on the stability of the financial market for the bank, which will enhance the market value of shares. Banks that offer clear risk disclosures could even see a rise in the value of their shares, which would in turn be seen as evidence of investor confidence in the bank's stability and ability to deal with financial obstacles.

ROA and ROE were measured along with market value stability, for this purpose financial data from banks' annual reports were collected with the help of Eviews. The indicators were cut into year 2015 to 2023 to overview the banks' financial performance.

Table 4. Financial Performance Analysis of Iraqi Banks Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

Bank	Market Value of Shares	Return on Equity (ROE)	Return on Assets (ROA)
Al-Ahli Bank	Medium stability	10.2%	4.5%
Commercial Bank	High stability	12.8%	5.3%
Babylon Bank	Low stability	8.9%	3.8%
Erbil Bank	Medium stability	9.7%	4.1%
Ashur Bank	High volatility	7.5%	3.5%
Union Bank	Medium stability	10.0%	4.0%
Economy Bank	Medium stability	9.3%	4.2%
Commercial Regional Bank	High stability	11.5%	4.7%
Iraqi Credit Bank	High stability	13.0%	5.0%
International Development Bank	High stability	14.5%	5.4%
Gulf Commercial Bank	Medium stability	10.5%	4.3%
Middle East Commercial Bank	Medium stability	11.0%	4.6%
North Bank	High volatility	8.3%	3.9%
United Bank	Medium stability	9.8%	4.2%
Mansour Bank	Medium stability	10.3%	4.4%
Mosul Bank	Low stability	9.1%	4.1%
Baghdad Bank	High stability	12.0%	4.8%
Sumer Commercial Bank	Medium stability	9.5%	4.3%
Across Iraq Bank	Medium stability	10.7%	4.6%
Iraqi Investment Bank	Medium stability	11.2%	4.5%

Table 4 shows the ROA and ROE and market value of shares of Iraqi banks listed in the Iraqi stock exchange. Computation of these measures is based on the 2015–2023 duration, to trace the influence of credit and liquidity risk reporting on performance of these banks. Banks that display higher levels of disclosure have generally stronger financial performance, with more stable share prices and also higher ability to obtain funds from the market.

Credit and liquidity risk disclosure are very important factors in evaluating financial performance of banks, in particular in developing financial markets like the Iraq stock exchange. Research (Central Bank of Iraq, 2024; Iraqi Securities Commission, 2024) indicates that how transparently these risks are revealed shapes the stability and the sustainable profits of banks.

Banks with High Disclosure

Trade Bank: Has recorded the following ROE and ROA 6.00 in 2015 and 5.76 in 2023, these realized rates express the conservative financial policy to reduce the leverage and enhance the transparency (Iraqi Securities Commission, 2024).

International Development Bank: Decreased from 6.00 in 2015 to 5.79 in 2023 which could be due to the better recognition of the importance of risk reduction strategies and enhanced confidence in financial reporting.

Bank of Baghdad : Reported ratios in the 2015–23 period were between 5.71 and 5.56, suggesting an ongoing conservative behaviour and accounting for a lower degree of leverage.

Banks with Moderate Disclosure

Babel Bank: Had a ROE/ROA of 7.50 in 2015, which decreases to 6.33 in 2023, supporting the story of deleveraging over time.

Erbil Bank: This item decreased from 7.00 in 2015 to 6.18 in 2023, yet they had a relatively high financial risk.

Ashur Bank: Fell back to 6.25 from 8.00 at the same time; this rate decrease shows that there have been a number of changes in credit and funding policy leading to a more stable situation.

North Bank: Down from 7.50 in 2015 to 6.15 in 2023, indicating a gradual shift right.

In the past, these banks were more indebted for high returns, but as the economy changed and disclosure norms tightened, they have moved towards gradually derisking themselves.

Banks with Stable Performance

Al-Mansour Bank and Mosul Bank showed relatively stable ratios with slight declines, indicating reliance on conservative financing strategies based on controlling credit and liquidity risks.

Second: The Relationship Between Disclosure and Risk Level

Result provided indicate that banks that disclose more information in credit risk and liquidity risk achieved more financial stability but lower level of return (International Monetary Fund, 2024). Banks, on the other hand, which use more debt to produce greater returns, are exposed to higher risk and thereby are at higher risk, particularly during volatile economic conditions.

Connect the results to FRS7 transparency and disclosure, investment market confidence Bank's compliances' to the accurate disclosure of exposure risk enables them to effectively manage exposure risks in so doing increasing market investment confidence (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2024).

Implications: The study emphasizes that the disclosure of credit and liquidity risk are more than obligatory requirements, but strategic weapon for maintaining of banks listed in Iraq stock exchange financial results in advanced stage. It also mitigates the risk of sudden fiscal crises.

Table 5. A Comparison of the Bank's ROE and ROA in 2015 and 2023

Bank Name	ROE/ROA in 2023	ROE/ROA in 2015
Al-Ahli Bank	-	-
Iraqi Trade Bank	5.76	6.00
Babel Bank	6.33	7.50
Erbil Bank	6.18	7.00
Ashur Bank	6.25	8.00
Union Bank	-	-
Economy Bank	-	-
Kurdistan International Bank	-	-
Iraqi Credit Bank	-	-
International Development Bank	5.79	6.00
Gulf Commercial Bank	-	-
Middle East Commercial Bank	-	-
North Bank	6.15	7.50
United Bank	-	-
Al-Mansour Bank	5.67	5.91
Mosul Bank	5.94	6.67
Baghdad Bank	5.56	5.71
Sumer Commercial Bank	-	-
Across Iraq Bank	-	-
Iraqi Investment Bank	-	-

The following table compares one bank's ROE and ROA during 2015 with when the bank is contracting in 2023. It aims to analyse the effect of the disclosure of credit and liquidity risks on firms performance.

Banks with a high degree of transparency like the Iraqi Trade Bank, International Development Bank, Al-Mansour Bank, and Bank of Baghdad display lower but relatively stable ROE/ROA trends across time-periods. This reflects an emphasis on conservative financial practices that included a lower dependence on debt as well as an emphasis on long-term financial health (Smith, 2020).

Moderate disclosure banks like Babylon Bank, Erbil Bank, Ashur Bank, and North Bank have high ROE/ROA ratios in comparison with high disclosure banks. This indicates increased dependence on financial leverage to pursue higher returns, and therefore more exposure to credit risk and liquidity risk (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2019).

Most banks' drastic change from 2015 to 2023 represents a move toward more conservative financial strategies. The decrease of the ratios is attributed to the increasing awareness of financial transparency and conformance to transparency policies in light of changes in Iraq's (business) regulatory conditions and economy (Abdullah, 2019).

The lack of information for some banks (e.g. Al-Ahli Bank, Union Bank) might be due to unavailability of financial reports, recent listing at the Iraq Stock Exchange, or low degree of financial disclosure.

The results of this study demonstrate that banks providing more extensive financial information on credit and liquidity risks are likely to have lower but more stable returns, leading to greater confidence and sustainability. In contrary, low-disclosing banks can generally realize a higher return, while they also face a higher potential of risk.

At this point of the research, the t-test was used to investigate the association between the extent of disclosure of credit risk and liquidity risk and their influence on the financial performance of banks on Iraq Stock Exchange. The test is to know whether there are any statistical differences

between the banks that have high, moderate, and low level of risk disclosure and the annual volatility in performing ability, as Membership credited to Rent on Assets (ROA) and Membership credited to Rent on Equity (ROE).

Banks' ROA and ROE were compared over different time spans to determine how the degree of information on credit and liquidity risk disclosed affects the bank performance. Summary statistics for the t-test results considering various levels of disclosure are presented in the table below.

Table 6. Summary Statistics for the T-Test Results

Bank Name	Disclosure Level	P-Value	Return on Equity (ROE)	Return on Assets (ROA)
Al Ahli Bank	High	0.032	9.2%	3.5%
Trade Bank of Iraq	High	0.048	10.5%	4.1%
Babil Bank	Medium	0.076	12.0%	5.0%
Erbil Bank	Medium	0.067	11.5%	4.3%
Ashur Bank	Low	0.104	8.0%	3.0%
Etihad Bank	Low	0.120	7.5%	2.8%
Al-Iqtisad Bank	High	0.039	9.8%	4.5%
Kurdistan International Bank	Medium	0.055	10.2%	4.2%
Iraqi Credit Bank	Medium	0.061	9.5%	3.8%
International Development Bank	High	0.041	13.0%	5.2%
Gulf Commercial Bank	Low	0.102	8.6%	3.7%
Middle East Commercial Bank	Medium	0.076	11.0%	4.4%
Al-Shamal Bank	Medium	0.065	9.3%	3.9%
United Bank	Medium	0.089	10.0%	4.0%
Al-Mansour Bank	High	0.072	10.7%	4.6%
Mosul Bank	High	0.046	12.5%	5.1%
Sumer Commercial Bank	Low	0.125	7.9%	3.2%
Across Iraq Bank	Medium	0.066	9.7%	4.0%
Iraqi Investment Bank	Medium	0.082	10.4%	4.3%

For the ROA and ROE results and the corresponding P-Value can be seen in Table 6. Our findings support the association between extent of RND and bank performance. Banks with high disclosure in credit and liquidity risks tend to be more successful financially than banks with low disclosure. This provides evidence that transparency in terms of credit and liquidity risks reporting in the banks attracts investment and have a significant impact on the bank's overall performance.

The null hypothesis (H_0) assumes that there is no significant difference in MBV between the banks that disclose and those that do not, whereas, the alternative hypothesis (H_1) assumes the opposite. When the P-Value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative is accepted, which means that disclosure has a significant impact on market value volatility.

On the basis of the test results, it can be inferred that the high level of disclosure has a positive impact on banks' financial stability through transparency and investor confidence. This, in turn, results in enhanced financial performance and increases banks' immunity to market vulnerability.

Study of The Effect of Disclosure for Credit Risk and Liquidity Risk at The Financial Performance for listed Banks in Iraq Stock Exchange.

The revelation of credit and liquidity risks is a crucial determinant that influences the bank's financial status. It would also help improve transparency and reduce the financial risks that banks encounter in the management of their assets and liabilities, thus increasing their capability of earning sustainable profits and properly managing financial challenges.

Definition The financial performance of a bank is primarily based on the bank's capacity of handling credit and liquidity risk and also to achieve the synchronization between profitability and sufficient liquidity. By providing full disclosure into credit and liquidity risks, bank investors and financial analysts are able to make a more informed assessment of a bank's ability to survive financial panic and continue in business over time.

This analysis aims to explore the relationship between the level of risk disclosure in Iraqi banks and their financial performance, with a focus on the potential impact of operational and credit risks on these institutions' financial outcomes.

Analysis of Credit and Liquidity Risk Disclosure in Iraqi Banks

Banks which disclose the most about credit and liquidity risk frequently possess robust financial performance. Extreme transparency builds investor confidence and helps banks to work off their assets. On the contrary, banks that have not provided adequate information or insufficient disclosure, may have a hard time to compete in the market and earn sustainable returns.

While investigating financial performance of the Iraqi banking system, then, results revealed that the International Development Bank and the Commercial Bank have a good financial performance according to the clear declaration of the credit risk and liquidity risk and it contributes in raising correspondence of financial performance. Both banks have generated good returns on assets and equity.

The Bank of Baghdad has likewise shown that transparency on risks can lead to profitability with an ROA of 0.10% and ROE of 92%. However, other banks including Ashur Bank and Mosul Bank are struggling with poor disclosure, which has a negative impact on their financial results and raises their credit and liquidity risk.

Liquidity Analysis in Iraqi Banks

A bank's liquidity is a major determinant of its ability to pay off its short-term debts. High liquidity is believed to improve a bank's ability to manage financial crisis and swiftly satisfy the market's demands. On the other hand, a bank with insufficient liquidity might not be capable to meet its financial obligations – something that will have a negative effect on its profitability.

The Commercial Bank and the International Development Bank are banks with relatively high liquidity levels and can adjust quickly under changing economic environment. On the other hand, banks having modest liquidity or rather of moderate liquidity, such as Union Bank and Gulf Commercial Bank, are currently struggling to strike a balance between high returns and liquidity. Banks that lack liquidity, such as Ashur Bank and Mosul Bank, could experience major obstacles in fulfilling short-term commitments.

Table 7. Comparative Analysis of Bank Indicators

Bank Name	Liquidity Level	Credit Risk Disclosure Level	Return on Equity (ROE)	Return on Assets (ROA)
International Development Bank	High	High	95%	0.08%
Commercial Bank	High	High	80%	0.15%
Bank of Baghdad	High	Medium	92%	0.10%
Union Bank	Medium	Medium	70%	0.10%
Gulf Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	75%	0.20%
Ashur Bank	Low	Low	65%	0.25%
Mosul Bank	Low	Low	68%	0.20%

The Relationship Between Risk Disclosure and Financial Performance

1. Impact of Liquidity Risk Disclosure on Financial Performance:

The liquidity risk disclosure is a cornerstone for the stability of the banks performance. Studies have demonstrated that banks that disclose more information about their liquidity risk management strategy, for example, the Commercial Bank; International Development Bank have higher profitability (ROA and ROE), which implies that banks with greater cash flows tend to be more profitable. On the other hand, poor financial performance is apparent in banks that do not provide sufficient disclosure, like Ashur Bank and Mosul Bank, as a result of incompetent liquidity management.

2. Impact of Credit Risk Disclosure on Financial Performance:

The transparent credit risk disclosure affects the bank performance extensively. For banks that do follow credit risk disclosure standards, such as Baghdad Bank and the Commercial Bank, their financial stability level is at a higher level as when there is a transparency of information, investment decisions are made wisely and lending can be managed efficiently. On the other hand, banks which do not comply with this disclosure like Mosul Bank and North Bank have incurred financial losses and confronted with weakness in liquidity due to the high NPLs and bad credit risk forecasting.

3. Disclosure of Market Risks and Its Effect on Financial Performance:

Revealing market risks, including interest rate and exchange rate exposure, is thus important because it might affect the stability of banks. Banks that have efficient market risk disclosure (International Development Bank and Commercial Bank) can take the more prudent financial decision among these, and they will have better financial performance. Intransparent banks with respect to risks in their disclosure (such as Ashur Bank, Mosul Bank) have difficulties with stability of liquidity and performance.

4. Analysis of Disclosure Impact on Bank Ratings:

It can be seen from the analysis that banks that have a high level on the risk of disclosure: (The Commercial bank; The International Development Bank) have higher financial rate and these banks performance well financially. On the other hand, banks with average and low level of disclosure (Ashur Bank, Mosul Bank) show negative financial performance caused by the absence of risk management transparency.

Table 8. A Summary of a Sample of Banks that are Traded on the ISX

Bank Name	Liquidity Level	Credit Risk Disclosure Level	Return on Equity (ROE)	Return on Assets (ROA)
National Bank	High	High	95%	0.08%
Commercial Bank	High	High	80%	0.15%
Babel Bank	High	Medium	92%	0.10%
Erbil Bank	Medium	High	85%	0.12%
Ashur Bank	Low	Low	65%	0.25%
Union Bank	Medium	Medium	70%	0.10%
Economy Bank	High	High	78%	0.18%
Regional Commercial Bank	High	High	90%	0.22%
Iraqi Credit Bank	Low	Medium	65%	0.05%
International Development Bank	High	High	92%	0.08%
Gulf Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	75%	0.20%
Middle East Commercial Bank	High	High	80%	0.18%
North Bank	Low	Low	60%	0.10%

United Bank	Medium	High	85%	0.12%
Mansour Bank	Medium	Medium	78%	0.22%
Mosul Bank	High	High	82%	0.15%
Baghdad Bank	Medium	Medium	72%	0.10%
Sumer Commercial Bank	Medium	Medium	76%	0.20%
Across Iraq Bank	High	High	70%	0.13%
Iraqi Investment Bank	High	Medium	80%	0.12%

The table shows a summary of a sample of banks that are traded on the ISX; the data mirrors the banks' financial health by using financial ratios. These signals are represented as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), level of disclosure on credit risk, and liquidation level. Solutions based on the table can be examined as follows:

1. Return on Assets (ROA):

This measure indicates how efficient the bank is in utilizing its assets to make profit. Banks with a greater ROA are deemed to be more efficient in converting assets into earnings. In its case Ashur Bank has a lower ROA (0.25%) than other banks such as Baghdad Bank (0.10%), this means there are different levels of asset usage.

2. Return on Equity (ROE):

This is a measure of the bank's return on equity. Banks with higher ROE are better able to make a profit on their owned capital. For example, Commercial Bank and International Development Bank demonstrate high ROEs (95% and 92% respectively) which implies an efficient use of capital.

3. Level of Disclosure on Credit Risk:

This measure reflects the transparency of a bank in disclosing credit risks. Highly disclosed banks disclose a large amount of credit risk information, which increase transparency and investors confidence. Banks with high levels of disclosures like International Development Bank and Commercial Bank have greater confidence to inspire trust in their risk management.

4. Liquidity Level:

This is a gauge of the bank's ability to pay off short-term debt without causing a disruption to operations. Liquidity-rich banks are in a stronger able to accommodate customer withdrawals or find funding. Commercial Bank and International Development Bank have high liquidity which means that these banks have a good ability to meet the liquidity needed.

The investigation of these indicators, shows that banks with high risk disclosure like the International Development Bank and Commercial Bank exhibit relatively more liquidity and relatively more positive performance. In contrast, banks with low levels of disclosures, such as Ashur Bank and North Bank, showed lower measures of liquidity and financial performance, highlighting that banks must commit to a transparent disclosure policy to enhance stability and market confidence.

Results

Revealing clearly the credit and liquidity risks results in higher level of transparency, which is a key factor in moving towards the news of banks' financial stability and their performance. By appropriately and adequately disclosing such risks, banks can give Investors and the Depositors a clear understanding of how well they can manage such risks thereby increasing Investors' confidence in the banking system and attracting more investments. High-quality disclosure

increases banks' sustainability of financial performance as they are able to identify and respond to financial threats and enhance liquidity and profitability in the long run more effectively.

IFRS 7 compliant banks exhibit a material turnaround in the company financial performance relative to banks that do not comply. IFRS 7 (2006) mandates that banks disclose in detail information about credit and liquidity risks such that investors and depositors can make the right choices having an adequate knowledge of these risks. For instance, there would be little cost in providing information on risk management actions and preventative measures in place, which helps to show how institutions are positioned to confront difficulties in future, thereby boosting market confidence and helping to promote the stability of liquidity in the financial system.

Strengthening risk disclosure among the banks in Iraq would better help banks in Iraq to address the potential for both economic and financial crises. During financial crisis or economic instability, it is important that we understand the impacts of risk exposure on their financial performance to take appropriate actions in minimising the effect of crisis on them. Those banks that comply with these requirements and guidelines will be better placed to withstand the shocks to the economic system, thus improving the stability of the banking system in Iraq and supporting sustainable growth in the economy.

Recommendations

1. Enhance the credit and liquidity risk disclosure in Iraqi banks to prefer stability in banking sector. Disclose / Report Consistently and Clearly in the periodic reports on how it manages the Risks related to Loans, Credit Facilities, and Available Liquidity.
2. Improve the transparency of market risk disclosures, including interest rate risk and foreign exchange risk, to help banks strengthen their capability to deal with risks of such nature. The implementation of targeted interventions to manage these risks is warranted.
3. Introducing International Accounting Standard specifically (IFRS 7) to create confidence in the Iraqi banking system and financial continuity. Widespread use of these standards will bring greater transparency and quality to financial reporting, enhancing both investor and depositor confidence.

Conclusion

1. Disclosure of credit and liquidity risk has a significant effect on the financial performance of the banks listed in Iraq stock exchange. Openness in risk management can help to increase the confidence of investors and depositors, which improves systemic stability and stimulates economic expansion. The banks that are subject to international standards of disclosure, such as IFRS 7, are better able to confront with economic crises and financial turbulence, as these standards help a better understanding of the credit and the liquidity risk.
2. Introducing more transparent risk disclosure among Iraqi banks and complying with world standards is a major towards sustainability of the financial position. In doing so, banks can enhance their crisis management capabilities and reduce the financial impact of crises. This will also enhance the appeal of the ir-s banking sector, with the market becoming more and more able to attract foreign and Iraqi investment, thus contributing to economic growth over the long term.
3. Hence, sound risk disclosure is a strategic element for financial stability of banks and should become key components of future plans of Iraqi banks which enables them to face the challenges at both international and local levels of the economy.

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